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CELEBRATION OF THE ANNIVERSARIES OF HISTORICAL FIGURES AND CITIES IN OUR COUNTRY IN COOPERATION WITH UNESCO DURING THE YEARS OF INDEPENDENCE

Annotation: This article focuses on the study of the celebration of anniversaries of historical figures and cities in our country in collaboration with UNESCO during the years of independence. The research examines how, after gaining independence, our country integrated into the global community, established cooperative relations with international organizations, and hosted major conferences in collaboration with these organizations. It also highlights the joint celebration of anniversaries of historical figures and cities with UNESCO, as well as the analysis of studies related to ancient cities, their cultural monuments, and efforts for their restoration and preservation. Relevant regulatory documents, scientific research, literature, and periodical press materials have been utilized in elucidating the topic.

Keywords: Republic of Uzbekistan, UNESCO, Tashkent, Samarkand, Bukhara, Khiva, Karshi, Shakhrisabz, Margilan, Kok-Gumbaz, Ak-Saray, cultural monuments.

Аннотация. Данная статья посвящена изучению празднования юбилейных дат исторических личностей и городов в нашей стране в сотрудничестве с ЮНЕСКО в годы независимости. В исследовании рассматривается, как наша страна, достигнув независимости, присоединилась к мировому сообществу и наладила сотрудничество с международными организациями, а также организация крупных мероприятий в стране в партнерстве с международными организациями. Особое внимание уделяется юбилеям исторических личностей и городов, которые отмечались в сотрудничестве с этой организацией, а также исследованиям, связанным с древними городами и культурными памятниками, их реставрацией и восстановлением. При освещении темы использовались соответствующие нормативные документы, научные исследования, литература и материалы периодической печати.

Ключевые слова: Республика Узбекистан, ЮНЕСКО, Ташкент, Самарканд, Бухара, Хива, Карши, Шахрисабз, Маргилан, Кок-гумбаз, Оксарой, культурные памятники.

Our country has been making a worthy contribution to world civilization with its ancient statehood history, rich culture, national values, and immense scientific heritage. It is the land that nurtured great scholars who made significant contributions to the advancement of global science, such as Ahmad al-Fergani, Abu Ali ibn Sina, Abu Rayhan Beruni, Muhammad al-Khwarizmi, Abu Nasr Farabi, Imam Bukhari, and Mirzo Ulughbek. Furthermore, with its ancient cities and cultural centers like Samarkand, Bukhara, Khiva, Shahrisabz, Karshi, Tashkent, Termez, and Margilan, Uzbekistan is recognized by the global community as a country with a deep and rich history.

Today, numerous large-scale conferences are being held in Uzbekistan in collaboration with various international organizations, demonstrating the country's growing prestige and influence in the international community. Uzbekistan has been effectively cooperating with UNESCO, a specialized agency of the United Nations, in the fields of science, education, culture, and the preservation of historical heritage. As a result of Uzbekistan's membership in UNESCO and its cooperative relations with the organization, the anniversaries of several cities, great scholars, and historical figures have been widely celebrated at the international level.

Even during its time as part of the former Soviet Union, Uzbekistan celebrated the millennial anniversaries of encyclopedic scholars Abu Rayhan Beruni (1973) and Abu Ali ibn Sina (1980), as well as the 1200th anniversary of Muhammad ibn Musa al-Khwarizmi (1983) under the auspices of UNESCO. After gaining independence, the country intensified its efforts to commemorate anniversaries in collaboration with UNESCO.

From "1994" to "2010," Uzbekistan internationally celebrated the anniversaries of "six" historical figures, "eight" ancient cities, "one" national epic, "one" ancient historical heritage, and "one" historical scientific institution[1]. During the years of independence, the tradition of celebrating the anniversaries of historical figures within the framework of UNESCO began with the commemoration of the "600th" birth anniversary of Mirzo Ulughbek, a ruler and scholar from the Timurid dynasty[2]. A special joint event plan was developed between the UN office in Uzbekistan and UNESCO, and Mirzo Ulughbek's anniversary was widely celebrated both nationally and internationally.

The anniversary of Amir Temur, the founder of the Timurid dynasty, a great commander, a patron of science, and the ruler who restored the Great Silk Road, was widely celebrated both in our country and abroad. In honor of Amir Temur's anniversary, statues were erected in Tashkent, Samarkand, and Shahrisabz. In 1996, the 660th anniversary of Amir Temur's birth was celebrated on an international scale at the organization's headquarters in Paris in cooperation with UNESCO, the French Association for the Study of the "History and Culture of the Timurid Era," and the "France-Uzbekistan" Friendship Society. As part of these events, an exhibition titled "The Flourishing of Science, Culture, and Enlightenment in the Timurid Era" was opened at UNESCO headquarters[3]. An international conference on "The Flourishing of Science and Culture in the Timurid Era" was held with the participation of Timurid scholars from around the world, featuring 16 major scientific presentations[1]. Within the framework of these international events, the book and exhibition "The Culture and Art of the Timurid Era" were prepared.

In 1998, in our country, the 1225th anniversary of the birth of the great scholar Imam al-Bukhari and the 1200th anniversary of Ahmad al-Farghani were celebrated in collaboration with the organization, as well as the 545th anniversary of the great artist Kamoliddin Behzod in 2000, and the 900th anniversary of Abduholiq G'ijduvani in 2003[1]. In September 2023, the 1050th anniversary of the encyclopedic scholar Abu Rayhan Beruni was celebrated at UNESCO headquarters. The decision to widely celebrate Abu Rayhan Beruni's 1050th anniversary was approved at the 211th session of the UNESCO Executive Board[5]. The 200th anniversary of the Karakalpak poet Ajiniyoz Qosiboy o'g'li was included in the list of UNESCO international anniversaries for the next two years (2024-2025)[5]. In the coming years, the tradition of celebrating the anniversaries of our great scholars in our country will continue, strengthening cooperation between the organization and our country.

In 1997, the 2500th anniversary of the cities of Bukhara and Khiva was celebrated internationally in cooperation with UNESCO. In honor of the anniversary, historical monuments in Khiva and Bukhara were restored. A total of 259.1 million UZS was allocated for the restoration of historical and cultural landmarks in these cities. Of this amount, 74 million UZS was spent on the restoration of historical monuments in Khiva, while 185.1 million UZS was allocated for Bukhara[10].

In November 1999, at the 30th session of the UNESCO General Conference, a decision was made to widely celebrate the 2500th anniversary of the city of Termez on an international level. Based on this decision, on December 27, 1999, the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan adopted a resolution titled "On Preparing for and Celebrating the 2500th Anniversary of the City of Termez"[6]. In honor of Termez's 2500th anniversary, restoration and reconstruction work amounting to 270 million UZS[10] was carried out at historical sites, including Qirqqizqala, the Sultan Saodat

complex, the Kokildor-ota khanqah, Fayoztepa, Qoratepa archaeological monuments, and the mausoleum of Abu Iso at-Termizi. In 2002, the 2500th anniversary of Termez was widely celebrated.

In 2002, the 2700th anniversary of one of the ancient cities of our country, Shahrisabz, was widely celebrated in cooperation with UNESCO. On March 29, 2002, the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan adopted a resolution titled "On Preparing for the Celebration of the 2700th Anniversary of the City of Shahrisabz." According to Annex 3 of this resolution[6], restoration and reconstruction work amounting to 980.5 million UZS was carried out on historical and cultural monuments in the city. Conservation, restoration, strengthening, and beautification efforts were implemented in ancient historical centers such as the Oqsaroy, Doruttilovat, and Dorussaodat complexes, the Chorsu trading center, and the Chubiya[3] madrasa.

At the 31st session of the UNESCO General Conference, a resolution was adopted to celebrate the 2700th anniversary of the founding of Shahrisabz. Additionally, based on Resolution No. 452 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan, dated September 29, 2004, restoration work was carried out on historical monument complexes in connection with the 2700th anniversary of the city of Qarshi[7]. During the years of independence, opportunities arose to study, restore, and reconstruct historical monuments in Qarshi as well. The city's historical landmarks were mainly renovated in honor of historical figures and the 2700th anniversary of Qarshi.

At its 32nd session, the UNESCO General Conference recognized Qarshi's urban planning culture and adopted a resolution to celebrate its 2700th anniversary as a grand event[8]. With UNESCO's participation, the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan adopted a resolution on September 29, 2004, titled "On Preparing for the Celebration of the 2700th Anniversary of the City of Qarshi," outlining an extensive plan of events and launching large-scale construction efforts. As a result, in 2006, the 2700th anniversary of Qarshi was celebrated.

The year 2007 was a productive one for the cooperation between UNESCO and Uzbekistan in celebrating the anniversaries of ancient cities. During this year, the 2000th anniversary of the city of Margilan and the 2750th anniversary of the city of Samarkand were widely celebrated on an international scale under UNESCO's auspices.

On November 9, 2005, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan issued a resolution titled "On Celebrating the 2000th Anniversary of the City of Margilan"[9]. In connection with this, during the 33rd session of the UNESCO General Conference in 2005, a resolution was adopted regarding UNESCO's participation in the celebration of Margilan's anniversary. As a result, restoration and renovation work was carried out at 35[10] historical and cultural monuments in Margilan, including the Pirsiddiq complex, Ulugmozor pilgrimage site, the mausoleum, and museum of Jahon otin Uvaysiy.

On July 25, 2006, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan issued a resolution titled "On Preparing for and Celebrating the 2750th Anniversary of the City of Samarkand"[11]. In this regard, large-scale restoration work was also carried out on historical and cultural monuments in Samarkand. On May 7, 2007, at UNESCO's office in Paris, a scientific-practical conference titled "The Role of Margilan and Samarkand in World Civilization" was held, with the participation of prominent Uzbek and international scholars[3].

In 2009, in collaboration with UNESCO, the 2200th anniversary of Tashkent, the capital of Uzbekistan, was widely celebrated internationally. A resolution regarding this was adopted at the 34th session of the UNESCO General Conference on November 2, 2007. On April 2, 2008, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan issued a decree titled "On Preparing for and Celebrating the 2200th Anniversary of the City of Tashkent"[13], followed by another decree on June 10, 2009, titled "On Holding the Main Celebrations Dedicated to the 2200th Anniversary of the City of Tashkent"[14]. In connection with this, events dedicated to the 2200th anniversary of Tashkent were held at UNESCO's

headquarters in Paris. During these events, the then Director-General of UNESCO, K. Matsuura, participated and highly praised Uzbekistan's efforts in restoring its historical and cultural heritage, as well as its cooperation with the organization in this regard.

During the years of independence, Uzbekistan, in collaboration with UNESCO, has widely celebrated the jubilees of various historical figures and cities. In 1997, the 2,500th anniversaries of the cities of Bukhara and Khiva were commemorated internationally. In 2002, the 2,500th anniversary of Termez and the 2,700th anniversary of Shahrisabz were celebrated. The year 2006 marked the 2,700th anniversary of Qarshi and the 1,000th anniversary of the Khorezm Ma'mun Academy. In 2007, the 2,750th anniversary of Samarkand and the 2,000th anniversary of Margilan were widely observed. In 2009, the 2,200th anniversary of Tashkent was celebrated on an international scale.

Additionally, the anniversaries of our great scholars were also commemorated in cooperation with UNESCO. For instance, in 1998, the 1,200th anniversary of Ahmad al-Fergani, in 2000, the 545th anniversary of Kamoliddin Behzod, and in 2003, the 900th anniversary of Abduholiq G'ijduvani were widely celebrated. In 2023, the 1,050th anniversary of Abu Rayhon Beruni was marked at UNESCO's headquarters. These events have played a significant role in promoting Uzbekistan's cultural heritage on a global scale.

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